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**EVALUATION OF SALT TOLERANCE IN FOREIGN AND LOCAL RICE
GERMPLASM UNDER SALINE SOIL CONDITIONS OF THE KHOREZM REGION
BASED ON CLUSTER ANALYSIS**

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Abstract. *The salt tolerance of 67 rice genotypes was evaluated in the highly saline soils of the Khorezm region using cluster analysis. The samples were classified into 9 groups, identifying LD-2022.2 (Lider) and KC-2022.2 (Manzur) as the most promising genotypes. These varieties maintained 35–42% germination under severe salinity and are recommended as primary breeding sources for saline environments.*

Key words: *rice, salinity, cluster analysis, Khorezm.*

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is the cornerstone of global food security and serves as the primary food source for more than half of the world's population, particularly in regions such as Asia, Africa, and Latin America. The rice crop plays a crucial role in human calorie and protein intake, as Asian countries account for more than 90% of global rice production and consumption [1,2]. Global climate change and negative environmental impacts are posing serious challenges to world agriculture. In particular, soil salinization has become one of the greatest obstacles to ensuring food security. In the context of Uzbekistan, this problem is becoming more acute year after year. According to Saburov (2023), the reclamation state of lands and the degree of salinity in Uzbekistan are worsening under the influence of environmental factors [3]. Recent studies show that approximately 53% of the irrigated lands in the republic are salinized to varying degrees. For comparison, this figure was 44.7% in 2020, and the growth rate within such a short period demonstrates the extreme urgency of the problem. Tukhtashev and Norkulov (2021) emphasize that secondary salinization, resulting from the improper use of irrigated lands, is the primary reason for the deterioration of the soil reclamation state. The authors have scientifically justified the necessity of correctly selecting and cultivating salt-tolerant crops (e.g., sunflower, sorghum, fodder beet, and others) to ensure the effective use and improvement of the condition of saline areas [4]. B. G. Kodirov (2019) conducted a series of studies on cultivating rice varieties under optimal saline soil conditions and selecting high-yielding varieties, ultimately identifying local salt-tolerant varieties [5]. In conclusion of the literary source analysis, it is worth noting that research conducted on the selection of salt-tolerant rice varieties and the improvement of their cultivation techniques remains fragmented and does not fully meet the current demands of severe soil salinization and global water scarcity. It is precisely this scientific necessity—specifically, the investigation of salt tolerance, a problem that remained unaddressed for a long period, through modern approaches—that defines the relevance and urgency of our research.

Materials and Methods. As the research objects, 67 rice germplasm samples were studied, including accessions from China (27), Vietnam (14), South Korea (5), Russia (2), and local breeding lines (19). The varieties Nukus-2, Iskandar, and Lazurny were used as control standards. The experiments were conducted during 2023–2025 under the soil conditions of the Khorezm region, characterized by strong chloride-sulfate salinity (SO_4^{2-} : 0.874–0.959%) and low nutrient content (N – 22.8; P_2O_5 – 27.5; K_2O – 165–220 mg/kg, humus – 1.01–1.20%). The salt stress tolerance of rice germplasm samples was studied under laboratory conditions based on the methods of N.V. Vorobyov (1999) and G.V. Udovenko (1977). Statistical analysis of the research results was performed using ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) in StatView and OriginPro software packages.

Results of the Research. Rice samples were evaluated under various salinity scenarios in laboratory conditions. Based on a dendrogram generated using OriginPro software, the response of rice varieties to salt stress (chloride and sulfate) was analyzed by categorizing them into 9 main clusters (groups). Each cluster is distinguished by the germination rates of the varieties and their specific levels of salt tolerance. Cluster 1 (highlighted in red) includes the varieties LD-2022.2 (LIDER) and KS-2022.2 (MANZUR). These varieties maintained a germination rate of 35-42% even under the highest salinity levels (Variant 5: Cl > 0.2% and Variant 9: SO₄ > 3.0%), making them the most promising sources. Cluster 2, which groups varieties under strong salinity (Variant 4: Cl 0.1-0.2% and Variant 8: SO₄ 2.0-3.0%), includes accessions such as NZ-2022.2 (YO'LDOSH) and XITTOY-2.2. Their performance indicators under extreme conditions ranged between 28-36%, indicating their suitability for solonchak (saline) soils. Cluster 3 comprises stable-resistant samples, including the varieties OM-5451.2 and GG-2022.2 (GIGANT), particularly under Variant 8 (SO₄ 2.0-3.0%). It was observed that these varieties demonstrated identical stability, with indicators around 29-30% under both chloride and sulfate salinity. Cluster 4 includes accessions with good adaptability to saline environments, such as RK-2022.2, OL-2022.2, and Nukus-2 (Control). Under moderate salinity (Variants 3 and 7), their indicators ranged from 63.5% to 75.7%, while in extreme chloride environments (Variant 5), their survival rate was recorded at 21.5-27.4%. Cluster 5 comprises the group of samples IR-50404.2, OM-18.2, OM-7347.2, and FLU-21. This group shows a germination rate of 66.2-92.4% under sulfate salinity (Variants 6 and 7); however, under strong chloride stress (Variant 4), the indicators drop to 40.3-44.1%.

Figure 1. Clustering of rice germplasm samples under various salinity scenarios.

Cluster 6 includes the varieties Vietnam 1.2, TL-2022.2, and FLU-21-04.1. These varieties lose their germination capacity more rapidly as chloride ion concentrations increase, although they remain stable under low salinity. At low gradients of chloride environments (Variant 2: Cl 0.01-0.03%), they show results of 85.3-89.2%, but in extreme sulfate environments (Variant 9), their tolerance drops to 14.8-19.8%. Cluster 7 includes the varieties Sanet.2, EP-327-01, UZ-2022.2, and Diamond.2, which germinate well at low salt concentrations; however, at extreme points (Cl > 0.2%), their indicators fell below 10%. In moderate salinity (Variants 3 and 7), although a germination rate of 56.1-69.7% was observed, the indicators dropped sharply under very strong chloride salinity (Variant 5), reaching only 1.3-8.4%. In Cluster 8, the samples GS-59.2, DONGJIN.2, and Water 127-132.2 lost more than 70% of their biological potential even at moderate salinity levels (Cl 0.1-0.2%). Under strong salinity scenarios (Variants 4 and 8), germination ranged between 23.9-33.2%, with a decrease to 3.7-9.1% observed under extreme conditions (Variants 5 and 9). Cluster 9, comprising the samples UP TShD-26-13, KP TShD-22-13, and UP 33-09, showed almost no germination (0-1%) under extreme salinity and only exhibited positive performance in the non-saline control variants. These samples showed a

germination rate of 14.1–20.4% under strong salinity (Variants 4 and 8), while under the most severe salinity variants (Variants 5 and 9), the germination rate dropped to 0%.

Conclusions. Based on the obtained results and cluster analysis, 67 rice samples were categorized into 9 groups according to their salt tolerance. The most resistant varieties, LD-2022.2 (Lider) and KS-2022.2 (Manzur), belonging to Cluster 1, maintained the highest germination rate (35–42%) under extreme salinity ($Cl > 0.2\%$; $SO_4 > 3.0\%$). Stable samples from Clusters 2 and 3, such as NZ-2022.2 (Yo'ldosh) and GG-2022.2 (Gigant), demonstrated their suitability for solonchak (saline) soils with indicators of 28–36%. The moderately resistant variety Nukus-2 (control) from Cluster 4 showed good results under moderate salinity (63.5–75.7%), but performed poorly in extreme environments (21–27%). It was determined that the sensitive samples in Cluster 9 were completely lost (0%) under extreme conditions.

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